

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 6.22 First Dissemination workshop results

Public

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1. Summary

This document is a part of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Work Package (WP6). The goal of the deliverable D6.22 “First Dissemination workshop results” is to summary the 1st CYCLOPES Dissemination Event which was held on 20th of April 2022 in Brussels, Belgium.

Furthermore, D6.22 also highlights how the cooperation between CYCLOPES and selected external partners works in practice today, and how it could look like in future.

2. Introduction

The project dissemination activities’ are mainly focused on network extension and sharing of the results internally and among the identified stakeholders and audience of interest. Thus the project should first have an understandable stakeholders’ engagement approach to amplify the results and activities of other members of the cybercrime ecosystem – helping to maximise impact and positive change in the fight against different forms of cybercrime.

The CYCLOPES network stakeholder audience are delineated as follows:

Audience 1: Practitioners (i.e. LEAs) interested in the uptake of security research and innovation in relation to the fight against cybercrime. All CYCLOPES partners engage practitioners throughout the project timeframe by inviting relevant stakeholders to the projects’ events and workshops, by proposing that they take part in different initiatives and ask for their feedback on how CYCLOPES solutions can support enhanced resilience to cybercrime.

Audience 2: Industry including SMEs. CYCLOPES engage industry players with interests in cybercrime. This network is invited to participate in the CYCLOPES events, workshops and webinars and receives all supportive documents needed to actively participate in key activities.

Audience 3: Scientific community. CYCLOPES results and updates are delivering to the relevant EU and Member State organisations such as Universities, Research and Technology Organisations, research communities and institutes, as well as the private sector.

Audience 4: Policymakers. CYCLOPES identify and proactively contact with targeted audience and invite interested actors to the projects’ events and workshops. CYCLOPES reach policymakers on both a European (i.e. DG Home, DG Connect, DG Grow) and on Member State level.

These audiences are at the core of the main goals of the CYCLOPES Communication and Dissemination Plan. Throughout the duration of the project, CYCLOPES intends to build and sustain efficient audience relations in order to enable interaction between differing innovation parties, and build synergies with already established European, national and sub-national networks of practitioners.

3. 1st CYCLOPES Dissemination Event

3.1. Main goal of the event

Efficient dissemination during the CYCLOPES project ensures short and long-term success of the project. In any project, the dissemination is a fundamental activity to create project visibility and reach various target groups. Through yearly Dissemination Events, CYCLOPES would like to be sure that:

- Project outputs and outcomes are widely disseminated to the right target audiences.

- Stakeholders can contribute to the outputs development, evaluation and exploitation. Thus, they should be identified and encouraged from the start to proactively interact with the consortium partners on a systematic basis.

A crucial part of dissemination events is to present the main project findings to a large spectrum of stakeholders and ensure efficient interaction between CYCLOPES and relevant partners. These events foster network activities, raise awareness of the project and bring together relevant practitioners and stakeholders who may wish to join to the CYCLOPES network and its activities.

3.2. Summary of the event

On the 20th of April 2022, the 1st CYCLOPES Dissemination Event was held in Brussels, Belgium. The event was wonderfully hosted by the Belgian Federal Police who provided a hospitable atmosphere and comfortable space throughout the entire event. The audience was made up of around 40 people from LEAs across Europe, representatives from the following networks and organisations engaged in the fight against cybercrime in Europe: Europol Innovation Lab, EC3, ENLETS, ECTEG and European Judicial Cybercrime Network and CYCLOPES Consortium.

It is relevant to underline that the 1st CYCLOPES Dissemination Event was planned as a big event due to two reasons:

1. The preparations to the event, including selection of place, started in December 2021, with many COVID-19 restrictions and it was not known how many people would be allowed to join the physical meeting;
2. In the 1st year of the project's implementation, we focused mainly on the practitioners. Other external groups, like industry and research will be more involved in the following project years.

On behalf of Belgium Federal Police, Director-General Christiane Olbrechts, 1st Councilor International Police Operations and Cooperation Department, opened the event together with Rashel Talukder, the CYCLOPES Project Coordinator, who then introduced CYCLOPES. Then, leaders of particular work packages presented the scope of CYCLOPES as well as current activities and those planned in the near future. The presentations were given by representatives of:

- Home Office, UK
- Centre of Excellence in Terrorism, Resilience, Intelligence and Organised Crime Research (CENTRIC), UK
- Austrian Standards International (ASI), Austria
- Cybercrime Research Institute (CRI), Germany
- Dutch Institute for Technology, Safety & Security (DITSS), The Netherlands

Next, there were highly interesting practical presentations provided by practitioners from the Belgian Federal Police, sharing best practices and challenges in the area of fighting cybercrime.

The final point of the agenda was a discussion panel with representatives of following networks and organisations:

- Europol Innovation Lab,

- European Cybercrime Center (EC3)
- The European Network of Law Enforcement Technology Services (ENLETS),
- European Cybercrime Training and Education Group (ECTEG)
- European Judicial Cybercrime Network (EJCN)

The main goal of this session was to discuss how the cooperation between CYCLOPES and selected partners works in practice today, and how it could look like in future. Moreover, particular organisations and networks told about their expectations towards CYCLOPES project. Having representatives from each of them was hugely valuable, especially with regards to 'cooperation' - the main essential point for the CYCLOPES and its community.

3.3. Results of the event

The following key points from the discussion have been identified:

- 1) Exchanging and sharing information about different events, actions and relevant outcomes between different parties in the domain of fighting cybercrime should be increased. This apply also information to CYCLOPES events and outcomes.
- 2) CYCLOPES can be a good bridge between European LEAs and companies.
- 3) The process of selecting topics for next CYCLOPES workshops for practitioners' could involve also members of the panel discussion. Moreover, it would be better to go deeper into specific topics rather than wider and on a general level and to focus on the same topics in coming years, rather than constantly swapping.
- 4) A substantial part of the discussion was devoted to methodology of organising CYCLOPES practitioners' workshops. It was raised that more research should be done before the workshops to try and identify current state-of-the-art in specific field. In response, it was stated that CYCLOPES is identifying gaps and needs of LEAs, based on information delivered by representatives of particular LEAs.
- 5) Also based on last point it was raised that CYCLOPES could support more in disseminating to LEAs across European information about services and solutions already available and delivered by other parties – especially those on the panel.

The results of this 1st CYCLOPES Dissemination Event are very valuable for future CYCLOPES activities.

4. Conclusion

This document summaries the 1st CYCLOPES Dissemination Event which aim was to reflect on the CYCLOPES activities that took place during the first year of the project implementation.

Overall, the event was a success with insightful presentations that gave an insight into the progress that has been made, and the aspects to improve on going forward. During the productive discussion session, all invited stakeholders were able to input their thoughts and opinions in relevant matters especially those regarding CYCLOPES strategic direction and partnerships with pertinent initiatives.

The summary with the outcomes from this event was prepared for dissemination activities, and it is attached as Annex 1. The 2nd CYCLOPES Dissemination Event is planned for 2023.

Annex 1st CYCLOPES Dissemination Event Summary

THE CYCLOPES DISSEMINATION EVENT ON 20th APRIL 2022 IN BRUSSELS

The CYCLOPES project builds and maintains an innovation-driven network of Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) combating cybercrime. We identify solutions and research activities that help tackle the complexity of cybercrime - whilst eliciting priorities for standardisation and recommendations for innovation implementation and increased uptake.

On the 20th of April 2022 the **1st CYCLOPES Dissemination Event** was held in Brussels, Belgium to present the main project findings to a large spectrum of stakeholders and ensure efficient cooperation between CYCLOPES and relevant partners.

The audience **was made up of around 40 people** from CYCLOPES consortium, LEAs across Europe and representatives from the following networks and organisations engaged in the fight against cybercrime in Europe:

- Europol Innovation Lab
- European Cybercrime Center (EC3)
- The European Network of Law Enforcement Technology Services (ENLETS)
- European Cybercrime Training and Education Group (ECTEG)
- European Judicial Cybercrime Network (EJCN)

The event was wonderfully hosted by the **Belgian Federal Police** who provided a hospitable atmosphere and comfortable space throughout the entire event. The meeting was a great opportunity to reflect on the CYCLOPES activities that took place during the first year of the project implementation.

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On behalf of Belgium Federal Police, Director-General Christiane Olbrechts, 1st Councilor International Police Operations and Cooperation Department, opened the event together with Rashed Talukder, the CYCLOPES Project Coordinator, who then introduced CYCLOPES. Then, leaders of particular work packages presented the scope of CYCLOPES as well as current activities and those planned in the near future. The presentations were given by representatives of:

There were highly interesting practical presentations provided by practitioners from the Belgian Federal Police, sharing best practices and challenges in the area of fighting cybercrime.

The final point of the agenda was a discussion panel with representatives of following networks and organisations:

The main goal of this session

was to discuss how the cooperation between CYCLOPES and selected partners works in practice today, and how it could look like in future. Moreover, particular organisations and networks told about their expectations towards CYCLOPES project. Having representatives from each of them was hugely valuable, especially with regards to 'cooperation' - the main essential point for the CYCLOPES and its community.

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Key points from the discussion:

- 1 Exchanging and sharing information about different events, actions and relevant outcomes between different parties in the domain of fighting cybercrime should be increased. This apply also information to CYCLOPES events and outcomes.
- 2 CYCLOPES can be a good bridge between European LEAs and companies.
- 3 Longer discussion was dedicated to selection of topics for next workshops for practitioners. Following suggestions and remarks were made:
 - o Would be better to go deeper into specific topics rather than wider and on a general level.
 - o Sustained focus on the same topics in coming years, rather than constantly swapping.
- 4 A substantial part of the discussion was devoted to methodology of organising CYCLOPES practitioners' workshops. It was raised that more research should be done before the workshops to try and identify current state-of-the-art in specific field. In response, it was stated that CYCLOPES is identifying gaps and needs of LEAs, based on information delivered by representatives of particular LEAs.
- 5 Also based on last point it was raised that CYCLOPES could support more in disseminating to LEAs across European information about services and solutions already available and delivered by other parties – especially those on the panel.

At the end of this session, Rashel Talukder as a project coordinator informed that he would like to involve members of the panel discussion into the process of selecting topics for next workshops for practitioners.

The results of this event are very valuable for future CYCLOPES activities.
On the next day, 21st April 2022, during the General Assembly the consortium started the discussion how to update the activities in next project's year.

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